

Research article

New records of myxomycophagous beetle family Sphindidae (Coleoptera: Cucujoidea) from Bulgaria

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Abstract: New data on the distribution of the species *Aspidiphorus lareyniei* Jacquelin du Val, 1859, *A. orbiculatus* (Gyllenhal, 1808), *Odontosphindus grandis* (Hampe, 1861) and *Sphindus dubius* (Gyllenhal, 1808) (Coleoptera: Sphindidae) in Bulgaria are presented. The species *O. grandis* is reported for the first time from the country. Original photographs of all sphindid species occurring in Bulgaria are provided.

Keywords: *Aspidiphorus*, Balkan Peninsula, distribution, *Odontosphindus*, *Sphindus*

Introduction

Sphindidae (Coleoptera: Cucujoidea) is a small beetle family with worldwide distribution (Forrester & McHugh, 2010). Representatives of three genera are known for Europe: *Aspidiphorus* Dejean, 1821, *Odontosphindus* LeConte, 1878 and *Sphindus* Dejean, 1821 (Jelínek, 2007).

Adults and larvae of Sphindidae are exclusively myxomycophagous and can be found on or inside fruiting bodies (sporocarps) of slime molds, where they feed on spores and supporting structures (Burakowski & Ślipiński, 1987; McHugh, 2002; Forrester & McHugh, 2010). Adults of the Palearctic species *Aspidiphorus orbiculatus* (Gyllenhal, 1808) are known to hibernate under loose bark and leaf litter (Burakowski & Ślipiński, 1987). According to McHugh (2002), adult sphindids can be occasionally collected with flight interception traps, ultraviolet light traps or by Berlese funnel extraction.

Available data on the distribution of Sphindidae species in Bulgaria are scarce. Three species have been reported so far for the country. *Aspidiphorus lareyniei* Jacquelin du Val, 1859 has been recorded from Maleshevska Planina Mountains (Guéorguiev, 2006; Guéorguiev & Ljubomirov, 2009) and from

Belasitsa Mountains (Guéorguiev, 2011). *Aspidiphorus orbiculatus* (Gyllenhal, 1808) is known from Longoza Place (Kamchiya River Valley) (Guéorguiev, 2006) and from Belasitsa Mountains (Guéorguiev, 2011). Recently, *Sphindus dubius* (Gyllenhal, 1808) was reported from the vicinity of Ustrem Village, Sakar Mountains (Gradinarov, 2025).

In the present work, we report new localities of all previously recorded species of the family Sphindidae from different regions of Bulgaria. We also report a fourth species from the family for Bulgaria – *Odontosphindus grandis* (Hampe, 1861).

Methods

The main part of the material included in this study was collected from spring to summer 2020 in forest habitats in Western Rhodope Mountains, Central Stara Planina Mountains, Kamchiya River Valley and Upper Thracian Plain with flight interception traps. Most of the habitats studied are well-preserved deciduous forests, with sampling sites located near rivers. *Sphindus dubius* was also collected in a coastal oak forest in Rosenets Park (Southern Black Sea Coast of Bulgaria) with automatic light traps left

overnight (two 8W white and black tubes, powered by 12V batteries).

The photographs of the beetles habitus were taken with a Canon EOS R50 digital camera with Laowa 25mm f/2.8 2.5-5X Ultra Macro lens mounted on a WeMacro rail (Wemacro, Shanghai, China).

The examined specimens are preserved in the Zoological Collection of Sofia University, Faculty of Biology (BFUS).

Results

Order Coleoptera Linnaeus, 1758

Superfamily Cucujoidea Latreille, 1802

Family Sphindidae Jacquelin du Val, 1860

Subfamily Aspidiphorinae Kiesenwetter, 1877

Aspidiphorus Ziegler in Dejean, 1821

Aspidiphorus lareyniei Jacquelin du Val, 1859

Material: BULGARIA: Kamchiya Riv. Valley, NE of Dolni Chiflik Town, Longoza Place, near Kamchiya Riv., 43.012317°N, 27.726300°E, 19 m a.s.l., deciduous forest, 11–26.v.2020, 2 ♂♂ (BFUS-COL000647, BFUS-COL000648), flight interception trap, O. Sivilov & H. Hristova leg.; Upper Thracian Plain, S of Stara Zagora, near Sazliyka Riv., 42.386533°N, 25.626133°E, 176 m a.s.l., deciduous forest, 1–28.vii.2020, 1 ♂ (BFUS-COL000649), flight interception trap, O. Sivilov & H. Hristova leg.; Western Rhodopes Mts, SW of Peshtera Town, near Novomahlenska Reka Riv., 42.008633°N, 24.279817°E, 570 m a.s.l., hornbeam forest, 24.v–19.vi.2020, 1 ♀ (BFUS-COL000650), flight interception trap, O. Sivilov & H. Hristova leg.; the same data, 19–30.vi.2020, 2 ♀♀ (BFUS-COL000651, BFUS-COL000652); the same data, 30.vi–27.vii.2020, 1 ♂ (BFUS-COL000653), 4 ♀♀ (BFUS-COL000654–BFUS-COL000657).

Aspidiphorus orbiculatus (Gyllenhal, 1808)

Material: BULGARIA: Kamchiya Riv. Valley, NE of Dolni Chiflik Town, Longoza Place, near Kamchiya Riv., 43.012317°N, 27.726300°E, 19 m a.s.l., deciduous forest, 11–26.v.2020, 22 sex indet. (BFUS-COL000658–BFUS-COL000679), flight interception trap, O. Sivilov & H. Hristova leg.; Central Stara Planina Mts, SW of Chiflik Vill., near Beli Osam Riv.,

42.823450°N, 24.540833°E, 760 m a.s.l., beech forest (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) with solitary trees of *Populus tremula* L., *Abies alba* Mill. and other tree species, 13–28.v.2020, 3 ♂♂ (BFUS-COL000680–BFUS-COL000682), 2 ♀♀ (BFUS-COL000683, BFUS-COL000684), 8 sex indet. (BFUS-COL000685–BFUS-COL000692), flight interception trap, O. Sivilov & H. Hristova leg.; the same data, 4–30.vii.2020, 1 ♀ (BFUS-COL000693), 5 sex indet. (BFUS-COL000694–BFUS-COL000698); Western Rhodopes Mts, SW of Peshtera Town, near Novomahlenska Reka Riv., 42.008633°N, 24.279817°E, 570 m a.s.l., hornbeam forest, 24.v–19.vi.2020, 1 ♀ (BFUS-COL000699), 4 sex indet. (BFUS-COL000700–BFUS-COL000703), flight interception trap, O. Sivilov & H. Hristova leg.; the same data, 19–30.vi.2020, 2 ♂♂ (BFUS-COL000704, BFUS-COL000705), 4 sex indet. (BFUS-COL000706–BFUS-COL000709); the same data, 30.vi–27.vii.2020, 1 ♂ (BFUS-COL000710), 4 ♀♀ (BFUS-COL000711–BFUS-COL000714), 5 sex indet. (BFUS-COL000715–BFUS-COL000719).

Subfamily Sphindinae Jacquelin du Val, 1860

Odontosphindus LeConte, 1878

Odontosphindus grandis (Hampe, 1861)

Material: BULGARIA: Western Rhodopes Mts, SW of Peshtera, near Novomahlenska Reka Riv., 42.008633°N, 24.279817°E, 570 m a.s.l., hornbeam forest, 30.vi–27.vii.2020, 1 ♂ (BFUS-COL000720), 1 ♀ (BFUS-COL000721), flight interception trap, O. Sivilov & H. Hristova leg.; Central Stara Planina Mts, SW of Chiflik Vill., near Beli Osam Riv., 42.823450°N, 24.540833°E, 760 m a.s.l., beech forest (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) with solitary trees of *Populus tremula* L., *Abies alba* Mill. and other tree species, 4–30.vii.2020, 1 ♀ (BFUS-COL000722), flight interception trap, O. Sivilov & H. Hristova leg.

Notes: New country record for Bulgaria.

Sphindus Dejean, 1821

Sphindus dubius (Gyllenhal, 1808)

Material: BULGARIA: Black Sea Coast, Rosenets Park, NW of Atiya Vill., 42.444133°N, 27.553883°E, 30 m a.s.l., oak forest, 9–10.vii.2017, 1 ♀ (BFUS-COL000723), 1 sex indet. (BFUS-COL000724), at

Fig. 1. Species of Sphindidae in Bulgaria – (A) *Aspidiphorus lareyniei* (female, BFUS-COL000651), (B) *A. orbiculatus* (male, BFUS-COL000704), (C) *Sphindus dubius* (male, BFUS-COL000725), (D) *Odontosphindus grandis* (male, BFUS-COL000720), (E) *O. grandis* (female, BFUS-COL000721). Scale bars: 1 mm.

light (automatic light trap), Y. Petrova & D. Gradinarov leg.; Western Rhodopes Mts, SW of Peshtera Town, near Novomahlenska Reka Riv., 42.008633°N, 24.279817°E, 570 m a.s.l., hornbeam forest, 30.vi–27.vii.2020, 1 ♂ (BFUS-COL000725), flight interception trap, O. Sivilov & H. Hristova leg.; Central Stara Planina Mts, SW of Chiflik Vill., near Beli Osam Riv., 42.823450°N, 24.540833°E, 760 m a.s.l., beech forest (*Fagus sylvatica* L.) with solitary trees of *Populus tremula* L., *Abies alba* Mill. and

other tree species, 4–30.vii.2020, 2 ♀♀ (BFUS-COL000726, BFUS-COL000727), flight interception trap, O. Sivilov & H. Hristova leg.

Notes: Second record for Bulgaria.

Discussion

According to Jelínek (2007), the species *A. lareyniei* is distributed in Azerbaijan, Austria, Bosnia and

Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Italy, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia and South European Territory of Russia. The species has also been reported from Ukraine (Mateleshko, 2009), Spain (Viñolas et al., 2012), Greece and Poland (Królik & Lasoń, 2020).

In Bulgaria, *A. lareyniei* is known from Maleshevska Planina Mountains (surroundings of the villages Gorna Breznitsa, Palat, Igralishte, Nikudin and Sedelets) (Guéorguiev, 2006: 47; Guéorguiev & Ljubomirov, 2009: 252) and from Belasitsa Mountains (Guéorguiev, 2011: 12). Here we report the species from Kamchiya River Valley, Upper Thracian Plain and Western Rhodopes Mountains. *Aspidiphorus lareyniei* can be distinguished from *A. orbiculatus* by the lack of longitudinal grooves on either side of the frons, the paler colouring of the antennal club and the incised scutellar shield (Królik & Lasoń, 2020) (Fig. 1A, B).

Aspidiphorus orbiculatus is widespread in Europe (Jelínek, 2007), occurs also in North Africa (Algeria) and in a number of countries and regions in Asia (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Russia: West Siberia, Russia: Far East) (Jelínek, 2007; Temreshev, 2025). The species was recently reported from Mersin and Muğla provinces in Southern Türkiye (Göktepe et al., 2023; Harman & Avcı, 2023) and from Kazakhstan (Temreshev, 2025).

In Bulgaria *A. orbiculatus* has been reported from Kamchiya River Valley (Longoza Place, Nova Shipka) (Guéorguiev, 2006: 48) and from Belasitsa Mts (Guéorguiev, 2011: 12). Here we confirm the presence of the species in Longoza Place, nearly 70 years after it was collected there by Karnozhitsky (Guéorguiev, 2006) and also report the species from Central Stara Planina Mountains and Western Rhodopes Mountains.

Our data indicate that species of the genus *Aspidiphorus* are probably widespread in forest habitats in Bulgaria, at least in areas close to rivers. In the deciduous forests of Longoza Place (Kamchiya River Valley), as well above Peshtera Town (Western Rhodopes Mountains), both species co-occur.

According to Jelínek (2007), the species *O. grandis* is distributed in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Greece, Romania and Slovakia. The species has also been reported from France (Freeman et al., 2003), Italy (Audisio et al., 2008) and Ukraine (Mateleshko, 2009; Diedus et al., 2022). Given the known distribution of the species, its occurrence in

Bulgaria is not surprising and it has probably been overlooked in previous surveys. Here we report the species from two distant localities in the country – Western Rhodopes Mountains above Peshtera and Central Stara Planina Mountains above Chiflik Village. In both localities the species co-occur with *S. dubius*, from which it can be distinguished, in particular, by its 11-segmented antennae and its larger size (Freeman et al. 2003) (Fig. 1C–E).

Sphindus dubius is widespread in Europe and occurs also in North Africa (Algeria, Canary Islands) (Jelínek, 2007). The species was recently reported from Muğla province in Southwestern Türkiye as well (Harman & Avcı, 2023).

The species has recently been reported for Bulgaria based on a single female from Sakar Mountains (west of Ustrem Village) (Gradinarov, 2025: 47). Here we report the species from the Southern Black Sea coast of the country, from the Western Rhodopes Mountains and from the Central Stara Planina Mountains. The species appears to be widely distributed in Bulgaria.

The hornbeam forests in the Western Rhodopes above Peshtera Town seem to be suitable habitats for all four species occurring in Bulgaria. According to McHugh (2002) adult sphindids can be caught occasionally with flight interception traps. However, our data indicate that this method is highly effective for collecting the European species of the family.

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Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the author, reviewers, or subject editor.

Author's contributions

(using [CrediT](#))

Denis Gradinarov: conceptualisation, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, valida-

tion, visualisation, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing; Yana Petrova: investigation, methodology, writing—original draft; Ognyan Sivilov: data curation, investigation, writing—original draft.

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